

To what extent did the German youth *conform* to Nazi Ideology between 1933-1939?

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Section 1: Identification and evaluation of sources

Firstly, the secondary source “Hitlerjunge Schall” (2016) by the German Historian André Postert will be analysed, as this source contains an examination of diary writings of a former HJ member. The analysis of the thoughts and mind of a Hitler youth member by a historian links directly to the investigation. The origin of the secondary source is valuable to the investigation because it was published in 2016. Thereby, Postert has the benefit of hindsight which is seen in the comments and evaluation of Schalls diary. The source can give an insight into the life of a former HJ member and thus offers understanding as to how the youth was confessing to the Nazi ideology. Postert breaks this down and emphasises the importance of the “unique” diary, making the purpose of the source valuable. The content reveals Postert’s viewpoint, that the document shows clear confession of not only Schall but rather most of the German youth to Nazi ideology, which adds a value to this investigation.¹

Since the primary source used by Postert got revised multiple times, the reliability of the origin is limited. The diary displayed has pages are left out and that the chosen passages are stylistically slightly straited, without Postert explaining his methodology.² As Postert aims to reveal the thoughts of HJ members, no links to other primary sources to draw similarities are discussed, which limits the purpose of the source by using a single source. Lastly, the writing style of Schall is similar to Nazi propaganda content. For that reason, Postert argues, that the NS youth diaries reflect on the youth mindset. This shows however a limitation to his interpretation of the content, as diary writing was part of political engagement among HJ members, and therefore less personal.

Secondly, the memoir “A dossier to my former self” by Melita Maschmann is of high relevance to this investigation, as it provides a primary insight into the authors experience in the HJ from 1933 to 1938, where she describes in letter form style, how she conformed to the Nazi. Melita Maschman as the author is of value to the origin, for she has first-hand experience and was member in the HJ herself. Her purpose, to give an honest account of her life in the HJ can be considered as a value. As Maschmann explains her confession and conviction by saying “no word has never fascinated me as much as that of the *Volksgemeinschaft*”³, the sources content helps identify the appeal of the Hitler youth to young people.

¹ André Postert, *Die Hitlerjugend* (Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht, 2021). P338.

² Postert. P25.

³ Melita Maschmann, *Account Rendered: A Dossier on My Former Self* (London: Aberland-Schuman, 1964). P10.

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Melita Maschmann wrote the Memoir in 1964, many decades after the time of her experience in the Hitler youth. This can be a limitation to the validity of the source's origin, as her account of the past could have changed. Moreover, the intention to educate about the political viewpoint emerging from a nation seeking power and a dehumanisation on the other side, reasons of conformity might have changed in this prospect, as in 1964, the view of national socialism was viewed in a bad light which affects the purpose. Her claiming, that she shared the attachment to Hitler with "countless others" might lead to assumption for historians that the German generation felt like that without actual prove and shows the limitation of subjectivity seen in the content.

Section 2: Investigation

To make this investigation coherent, the interpretation of the terms Nazi ideology and conformity must be established in first place. The Nazi ideology in prospect to the German youth will refer to, the HJ, aiming to establish a *Volksgemeinschaft*, initially on the base of voluntarily and autonomous choice. When referring to the HJ, the *Bund Deutscher Mädel* (BMD) is included respectively. Conformity will refer to inwardly, meaning psychologically conforming, no resistance but neither belief in the Nazi ideology; the in-between, and non-conformity seen in opposition and resistance. Therefore, the investigation examining the question: *To what extent did the German youth conform to Nazi Ideology between 1933- 1939?* will be divided into, firstly addressing total conformity within the HJ, secondly superficial conformity within the HJ and thirdly resistance and opposition groups.

It could be argued that the German youth inwardly conformed to Nazi ideals between 1933-1939. The findings of many memoirs of former members of the HJ, as Michael H. Kater emphasizes, show that they felt pride being part of the HJ and the ability to hold power, superiority towards to non-HJ members made them reinforce their power.⁴ Maschmann confesses, that she had "clung herself to national socialism" and felt hope in "educating every German to be a decent National socialist".⁵ These characteristics go along with the Nazi ideology. In addition, the diary writings of former HJ member Franz Albrecht Schall, point towards the national belonging in the HJ and elaborate on his 'dedication' to National Socialism. Postert argues, that perhaps, this phenome was happening to many of his generation,

⁴ Michael H. Kater, *Hitler Youth*, Annotated (Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 2004). P1-3.

⁵ Melita Maschmann, *Account Rendered: A Dossier on My Former Self*. P12, 22.

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also after the *Machtübernahme*. However here must be critically questioned whether this argumentation considers those, who merely conformed to fit in. Apart from that, it must be pointed out, that the HJ membership was voluntarily, in fact there was no law until 1939 to force 10 to 18 year old into the HJ,⁶ yet 7.7 million were registered in Hitler youth by the end of 1938.⁷ Considering this, unexpectedly many young forces joined the *Kristallnacht* in 1938, the November program led by propagandist Goebbels. This evidence suggests that Nazi propaganda, exercised in schools, mass media and greatly in the Hitler youth, ensured little chances in formation in own values and beliefs of the adolescence.⁸ Some of their members went as far as violating opposition to the Hitler youth, with the goal of either dissolution or integration to their own ranks. Since this was the mayor task of *Reichs Jugend Führer* Schirach, and later the gestapo, the ideology got carried on within the HJ. That is seen in several clashes between HJ members and other groups after the *Machtübernahme*, one of them being the harassment against the *katholischer Jungmännerverband* where HJ members ripped of their signs from cloth.⁹ This argument is supported by Mommsens view, stating that the German youth rather exercised a potential threat to anyone willing to overthrow the regime, and generally stood aside.¹⁰ Therefore, the evidence shows how conformity inwardly among many young in Germany was present, but it must be seen respectively considering generalisations made by historians.

Even though, the number of HJ members rose drastically from 1933 on, this was perhaps not to a domestic conformity to national socialism, but rather an urged integration of the mass. The phenomena could be seen in urged integration of outside groups after the *Machtübernahme*. With Schirachs appointment to being *Reich* Youth leader, Kater stresses, that he used his power to ‘provoke peer pressure’ and make outside groups thereby join.¹¹ For instance, the *Bündische Jugend*, including the dj 1.11(*deutsche Jugenschaft*) and the *Wandervögel*, were the three youth movements prior to 1933, which got integrated into the HJ. The so called infiltration of the Hitler youth by former members of the *Bünde* was recognized by the gestapo, and some members managed to continue their activities within the HJ.¹² It

⁶ André Postert, *Die Hitlerjugend* (Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht, 2021). P249.

⁷ William L. Shirer, *The Rise and Fall of the Third Reich* (RosettaBooks, 2011). Chapter 8

⁸ Richard J. Evans, *The Third Reich in Power, 1933-1939* (New York: Penguin Press, 2005). P 585-7.

⁹ Kater, *Hitler Youth*. P21-22.

¹⁰ Hans Mommsen, *Germans Against Hitler*, 3rd ed. (London: L.B. Tauris& Co Ltd, 2009). P 38.

¹¹ Kater, *Hitler Youth*. P34.

¹² Walter Laqueur, *YOUNG GERMANY- A History of the German Youth Movement* (New Jersey: Transaction books, New Brunswick, 1962).

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stresses the view that entering the HJ after it's compulsion was not seen like initially in a revolutionary excitement among the adolescence.¹³ Quotes from a former HJ member: "We weren't fully conscious of what we were doing, but we enjoyed ourselves" may apply form majority of members of the Hitler youth, argues Koch.¹⁴ It underlines the lacking ideological conformity and awareness of Nazi youth membership. Furthermore, introduced by Hitler on December 1st ,1936, the 'law concerning the Hitler Youth' stating that "The entire German youth (...) is coordinated in the Hitler youth."¹⁵, was a measure of the Nazi to gain total control of the German youth. Koch interprets the law as making the HJ compulsory and argues that it led to many new HJ members joining, for no other reasons than for its compulsion.¹⁶ On the contrary, Postert argues there wasn't change in conformity visible with the introduction of the law, as no instruments were given to the state to implement the law. ¹⁷ This suggests, that after the *Machtübernahme*, and the 'law on the Hitler youth' superficial conformity and joining due to pressure instead of ideological appeal into the ranks of the HJ increased.

Lastly, there was a part of the german youth, which refused to conform to the HJ compulsion or even Nazi ideology. For instance, the Catholic youth movement refused to enter HJ and managed to organize trips, such as 2000 members pilgrimage to Rome in 1937. Although the catholic youth movement was allowed to continue its work, stated in Reichs Concordat between Vatican and German Reich 20. July 1933¹⁸, this opposition was religious and thereby non-conformist to the Nazi.¹⁹ Moreover, social opposition was especially seen in by the swing movement. Although not intending to overthrow or actively resist the Nazi ²⁰, McDonough argues they were a non-conformist group, as they did not attend the HJ and exercised illegal dances with up to 6000 people in bigger cities.²¹ Furthermore, the major political opposition were the Meuten, who were most active from 1937-9 with over 1.500 members in Leipzig. Emerged as "subculture" within working class, they wished for communist ideals of equality and opposed national socialism. Peukert points out, that

¹³ Postert, *Die Hitlerjugend*. P256.

¹⁴ H.W. Koch, *THE HITLER YOUTH, Origins and Development 1922-1945*, 1st ed. (London: Macdonald and Jane's, 1975). ,p94 -5.

¹⁵ Adolf Hitler, 'Law on the Hitler Youth', 1 December 1936,
https://ghdi.ghi-dc.org/sub_document.cfm?document_id=1564.

¹⁶ H.W. Koch, *THE HITLER YOUTH, Origins and Development 1922-1945*. P111-13.

¹⁷ Postert, *Die Hitlerjugend*. P259

¹⁸ H.W. Koch, *THE HITLER YOUTH, Origins and Development 1922-1945*. P110

¹⁹ H.W. Koch. P218-9

²⁰ Postert, *Die Hitlerjugend*. P329

²¹ Frank McDonough, *Opposition and Resistance in Nazi Germany*, Cambridge Perspectives in History (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2001). P17-8

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especially after the law on the Hitler youth, a considerably large group did not appeal to the education and leisure presented by the national socialists.²² On the contrary, Kater disagrees with this interpretation and puts the resistance groups and individuals into context and is of the position, that a “by far” greater part of the German youth was gathered in the HJ.²³ Koch adds, that many of the “gang” members, were already part of the Hitler youth and only formed in dislike of the compulsion of the Hitler youth.²⁴ This questions the extent of resistance, due to its motives. Apart from that, Angress argues that Jewish youth groups influence in Nazi Germany remained relatively big until the *Novemberprognom* 1938, with 97 different groups and 50.000 members in 1935.²⁵ It must be mentioned, that before the Nazi had total hold of the German youth in 1939, 4 million out of 11.7 million Germans managed to stay out of the HJ until the end of 1938.²⁶ The evidence highlights, that not the whole German youth conformed to the HJ, even if its number was respectively and some groups were as well part in the HJ.

The vast literature on the Hitler Youth as well as resistance, argues a shared historical viewpoint, which is that most of the German adolescence, between the years 1933-1939 did show conformity towards national socialism, mainly highlighted by the amount of HJ members. From then on, historical views split as to which extent and how nonconformity was present and in what it is defined. For nonconformity was present and the evidence suggests, that especially towards the second half of the 30s, conformity towards the Nazi and their ideology dwindled even within the HJ, opposing to the initial enthusiasm towards a bonding *Volksgemeinschaft*.

Section 3: Reflection

²² Detlev J. K. Peukert, *Inside Nazi Germany, Conformity, Opposition and Racism in Everyday Life* (New Haven: Yale University Press, 1987). P165, 173

²³ Kater, *Hitler Youth*. P28

²⁴ H.W. Koch, *THE HITLER YOUTH, Origins and Development 1922-1945*. P220

²⁵ Werner T. Angress, *Generation Zwischen Furcht Und Hoffnung, Jüdische Jugend Im Dritten Reich* (Hamburgh: Hans Christians, 1985). P25

²⁶ Shirer, *The Rise and Fall of the Third Reich*. Chapter 8

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This investigation has taught me the challenges and limitations that historians face when assessing primary sources. Limitations with the use of primary sources were rarely pointed out by historians, which could lead to blindly follow the power of quotes. The selection of primary sources can both display evidence of non-conformity and conformity, in memoirs, diaries, etc. Since investigating conformity meant, individual primary sources like memoirs, and private letters, historians could have get tricked by applying singular views to the mass. Koch for instance, suggesting that a view of a primary source may apply to most of the German youth is a limitation, as it is still, an individual source.²⁷ Unlike Friedrich Schall, not many young people from the age of 10 to 18 wrote diaries expressing their reflected views and opinions on politics and the Nazi ideology at that time. This challenges the validity of evidence, using only a selected or too small quantity of primary sources for investigations like conformity and consent.

The interpretation of conformity was further a challenge, as the definition of conformity varied from historian to historian, which led to different interpretations. For instance, Hellfred distinguished between five stages of conformity,²⁸ on the other hand historians like Kater analysed with the approach of the success of nonconformity to draw conclusions.²⁹ In addition, Kater only focused on the successes of the Hitler youth and how the state got rid of opposition rather than focusing “inwardly” conformity of its members. This made it harder finding explicit evidence explaining conformity. Further, historians like Mommsen, Peukert and McDonough paid much attention in their investigation to non-conformity and resistance, directing most of the book too it. This raised the question subjectivity, as the evidence created a viewpoint, suggesting more non-conformity than the reality. In my own investigation, I did the same by directing as many paragraphs to conformity as to non-conformity. This should however not highlight the quantity of evidence determining the interpretation. This remains an issue to historians in evaluating perspectives on an issue. For my investigation does in fact point out, that most of the German youth conformed to the Nazi ideology.

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²⁷ H.W. Koch, *THE HITLER YOUTH, Origins and Development 1922-1945*. P94-5.

²⁸ Von Hellfeld, Matthias, ‘Bündischer Mythos Und Bündische Opposition. Zu Einer Neubewertung Der Bündischen Tradition Und Ihrer Kulturellen Praxis’, in *Piraten, Swings Und Junge Garde, Jugendwiderstand Im Nationalsozialismus* (Bonn: J.H.W. Dietz, 1991). P100 et seq.

²⁹ Kater, *Hitler Youth*. P165.

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